

**WE, THE YOUTH, ARE AGAINST RELIGIOUS EXTREMISM,
TERRORISM, DRUG ADDICTION AND ANY FOREIGN IDEAS**

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Abstract. The article scientifically substantiates the fact that young people rely on knowledge and experience to combat any alien ideas and form ideological immunity. Today, the types of threats and methods of rapid impact have increased and are becoming more and more popular. The following types can be listed: religious extremism, international terrorism, drug addiction, mass culture, human trafficking, cosmopolitanism, gambling, missionary work, proselytism, nihilism, violence, neo-fascism, chauvinism, egocentrism, individualism, AIDS, starism (blind imitation of stars), vandalism (destruction of cultural and material monuments), immorality, prostitution, debauchery, same-sex marriages, happy hour (wild entertainment). The article emphasized the need to combat any alien ideas only through education.

Keywords: immunity, alien ideas, religious extremism, international terrorism, drug addiction, mass culture, human trafficking, cosmopolitanism, gambling, missionary work, proselytism, nihilism, violence, neo-fascism, chauvinism, egocentrism, individualism.

Today, in the context of globalization, “certain vices” that are not characteristic of humanity, spirituality and genuine culture, with their scope, influence and increasingly widespread nature, encroach on the national spirituality of the peoples of developing countries, trying to blur their essence and destroy them under the influence of “mass culture”. Such threats are realized through the media: television, the Internet or mobile phones, as well as through the economy, which is of decisive importance for the survival and livelihood of people. Based on this, one of the urgent tasks today is the formation of factors that can serve as protection against spiritual threats in the context of globalization, especially its impact on changing national customs, traditions, values and morals. To do this, it is important first of all to identify the essence of globalization, its advantages, as well as the threats that this process brings, and to conduct a scientific and theoretical analysis. The President of

the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated that “Today, when we realize the growing threat of various disasters around us, such as religious extremism, terrorism, drug addiction, human trafficking, illegal migration, “mass culture”, the deep meaning and significance of these words become even more obvious.” Indeed, at present, the education of youth remains a problem that will never lose its relevance and importance for us. “Today’s rapidly changing world opens up new and greater opportunities for humanity, for youth” [1]. In the modern conditions of national progress, increasing the spiritual development of youth, educating them as enlightened individuals has become an important priority in our country. This is a component of ensuring social stability and ensures the active participation of youth in the reforms carried out in the country. K. Kuronbaev noted that “In the context of building and developing a fair, democratic society, along with ensuring socio-political stability in the country, the affirmation of spiritual and moral values in the consciousness of the population is a fundamental change in people’s worldview and serves the development of the national development of Uzbekistan” [3, p. 52].

The problem of improving national ideology is now not only national, but also global. However, as N. Dzhuraev rightly noted [4, p. 76], the process of globalization is currently characterized not only by some abstractly positive moments, but also by the fact that it has given rise to «global problems of the modern era.» Many thinkers even call this period a period of global crisis. For example, «the twentieth century began with a strong sense of crisis and ended with this feeling» [5, p. 81], writes the Russian philosopher S.I. Dudnik. Indeed, although globalization has brought many positive aspects to modern society, it also reflects a stage in the development of mankind, at which the peoples of the world can no longer fight emerging problems alone, but can solve them together. Also among the most pressing tasks are the need to preserve national, cultural heritage and values in the context of globalization [6, pp. 486-491], the influence of the globalization process and spiritual threats on the spirituality of young people [7, p. 37-41], the role of the resolution «Spirituality and religious tolerance» in the fight against the threats of terrorism in the world [7, pp. 23-27], modern approaches to the process of globalization and intercultural integration [2, pp. 521-524]. The most urgent task in this regard is to comprehensively reveal the scientific and theoretical foundations of all processes, their new aspects, to explain them to our students and the general public in an accessible and concise manner, to turn them into active creators of building a society that meets the requirements of modernity. To do this, it is necessary, first of all, to further improve the system of creating specialized literature on each direction of our development - the development of political, socio-economic, spiritual relations in our society. The most important task in this regard is that every citizen, every person on this basis determines his duty and responsibility for the development and renewal

of society, as well as for the protection of our spiritual life from various threats and encroachments.

It is known that in order to prevent any disease, the human body first of all creates immunity against it. Therefore, in order to educate the younger generation of our country in the spirit of love for the Motherland, devotion to our rich history, devotion to the sacred religion of our ancestors, we need to strengthen the ideological immunity in their hearts and minds. So that our youth grow up as people who deeply understand their national identity and, at the same time, the world, and keep up with the times. Then even the ideas of ignorant fanatics who reject the concepts of morality and ethics and are completely alien to us cannot influence them.

What is invariable is that humanity has always fought: idea against idea, thought against thought, enlightenment against ignorance.

Protecting the younger generation from spiritual aggression, it is necessary to understand the undesirable habits that are common among our people and have long had a negative impact on its development, eliminate them or prevent the unpleasant situations that they cause, for they are evil, corroding the nation and society from within. First of all, the task of completely ridding our society of such vices as egoism and indifference, nepotism and parochialism, corruption and self-interest, disregard for others, falls primarily on the shoulders of broad sections of the population, especially the intelligentsia, scientists and writers, artists and cultural figures, people who have dedicated themselves to the sphere of spirituality. The feeling of envy, which has serious consequences for the life of a person and society, arises primarily from the inability to see others and, instead of rejoicing in their achievements, from bitterness and resentment. Our people, who have always been open, sincere and hardworking, highly valued kindness, have always been wary of such vices.

Another vice that poses a serious threat to our spiritual life is betrayal. It is no exaggeration to say that all evil is born of betrayal. A person who is not devoted to goodness and truth, who does not believe in them, is a terrible person. It is clear that a person with a traitorous nature will take a leadership position and disturb peace and tranquility. History shows that such traitors have often become the cause of civil and interstate wars in the country. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On measures to fundamentally improve the activities of the education sector» dated April 16, 2018: Widely promote the true humanistic essence of religion, that such virtues as goodness, peacefulness, humanity are an expression of our eternal values, and intensively organize scientific and educational activities in this area, based on the noble idea of »Enlightenment against ignorance»; Special attention was paid to such issues as the formation of the consciousness of the youth based on a deep study of the rich cultural heritage of our ancestors who made an invaluable contribution to Islam and world civilization [2], and the emphasis was

also placed on creating broad opportunities for deepening our people's understanding of their national identity by using our rich religious heritage to form tolerance, mutual trust and kindness in society.

In protecting the younger generation from spiritual aggression, it is necessary to understand the undesirable habits that are common among our people and have long had a negative impact on their development, eliminate them or prevent the unpleasant situations they cause, for they are an evil that corrodes the nation and society from within.

If a person suffers from a physical illness, it can be prevented and cured. The weakness of the spirituality of a nation is manifested in apathy, indifference, lack of enthusiasm, deceit in internal relations, rudeness, ignorance, selfishness, laziness and other vices of its character. Therefore, in order to heal the spiritual wounds that currently prevent us from improving, we need to approach this issue as a factor in studying and changing the true national character.

As a result, the country can join the ranks of the world's leading countries, improving its attitude to its situation, strengthening its positive sides and correcting and strengthening its shortcomings through education.

Society's confidence in its future does not arise by itself. It is based on a special activity - ideological education, that is, an activity aimed at the happiness of the nation, and therefore, for the benefit of each citizen. Ideological education does not consist in controlling people's worldviews, but in enriching their thinking, filling it with new meaning and content [10, p. 140].

The experience of the peoples of the world, the difficult paths of development they have gone through, the lessons and conclusions drawn from this experience indicate that wherever the state and society develop, where sufficient conditions are created for people to live peacefully and set noble and great goals, there reigns an atmosphere of free thinking and on this basis new opportunities for spiritual growth arise.

In ideological disputes, both the threatening and defensive sides use methods of popularizing the idea. These are ideological methods of education. Therefore, ultimately, victory will depend on propaganda and agitation based on scientific data. Thus, it can be said that the debate about ideologies turns into a debate about propaganda and agitation. Therefore, «the ideology of national independence must meet a number of requirements in order to become a national ideology in the true sense of the word.» One of these requirements is the ability to respond to any evil idea [11, p. 77].

Foreign ideologies cannot suddenly inject their ideas into society. They undermine the faith and hope of the nation that must first be destroyed in what it has believed in for so long. To do this, the things that the nation believes in are belittled

and discredited. As a result, the first stage of the breakdown of ideological immunity is achieved - the nation begins to be indifferent to the ideas and values in which it has long believed. Eternal values are no longer respected, and people tend to be indifferent to those who do not follow them. Values and ideas become useless and irrelevant. Thus, a void is created, «discovered».

Once an ideological vacuum is discovered, the idea of filling it begins to present itself in an attractive way. The «newness» and promises inherent in the subversive idea begin to penetrate the minds and hearts of people through their ears and eyes. In this way, the ideological vacuum begins to be filled. When a false idea penetrates the consciousness of people, it also becomes a great force. Turning to world experience, we see that the ideology of a nation is formed and improved over the life of not one, but several generations. The idea of forming a national idea, which is a banner uniting the entire people, found expression in works written in different periods of human history, and its vivid expression can also be found in the works of great representatives of ancient Eastern and Islamic philosophy [12, p. 364].

Throughout human history, there have been calls to strengthen ideological immunity and warn a nation left in stone about the tragedies that may occur if this is not achieved. Here is one of the methods of propaganda in the history of ideological struggle, including the causes and goals of rumors, as one of our great scientists Abu Rayhan Beruni wrote in the style of his time a thousand years ago [13, p. 67]:

«Truth and lies acquire a different meaning thanks to informants.» Because people have different goals; “There are many quarrels and quarrels between peoples,” he writes, and speaks of the obvious benefit of gossips’ lies: “...a person accuses another person of the opposite sex and spreads lies in order to boast, because in this way he has won (the opposite sex) and achieved his desire.

It is known that these two types of reports come from malice and anger. (The second person) spreads false news among them, wanting to thank the class he loves or to insult the class he hates. This type (announcer) will be close to the previous reporter. Because this rumor was spread as a result of friendship or enmity.

(Similarly) the third person also spreads false news in order to achieve some good due to his base nature or to avoid evil due to his heartlessness and cowardice.

There are also people who by nature are inclined to spread false news as if it were their duty and cannot rest without spreading false news. This is due to bad desires and dwelling in thoughts that are inherently evil.

Conclusion. Every student who has managed to instill a national idea in his mind and heart will be able to adequately respond to any destructive ideas, develop ideological immunity to alien and harmful ideas, and fight with dignity against various manifestations of fanaticism. Our society has always paid close attention to

ensuring socio-political stability. It is important not to allow and not to allow those trying to change the life of society to poison the minds of young people. The higher the ideological worldview of young people, the higher the national idea in the worldview of people, the broader the national idea in the worldview of people, the cleaner the social and ideological environment in our society will be. Of course, strengthening ideological education and ideological immunity among our youth is an urgent need, and for this it is necessary to strengthen this process at the level of family, neighbors and educational institutions.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Speech at the ceremonial meeting dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. www.press-service.uz.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On measures to radically improve the activities of the religious and educational sphere» // Khalk suzi, April 17, 2018
3. Kuronbayev K. Spirituality of the leader. - Tashkent, Tafakkur, 2017.
4. Juraev N. Theoretical foundations of the philosophy of history. - Tashkent: Manaviyat, 2008.
5. Dudnik S. I. Paradigmbi istoricheskogo mbishleniya XX veka: ocherki po sovremennoy filosofii kulturbi. SPb.: Sankt-Peterburgskoe filosofskoe obshchestvo, 2001.
6. Masharipova G.K. Globallashuv sharoitida milliy, madaniy meros va qadriyatlarni saqlash zaruriyati // “O‘zbekiston yoshlarini axborot urushi davrida mafkuraviy tajovuzdan asrash” mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari. - Toshkent-Denov - 2023 yil. - 486- 491-bb.
7. Masharipova G.K. The influence of globalization and spiritual threats on the spirituality of youth. // Collection of materials of the Republican scientific and practical conference on the topic «The role of spirituality in raising a healthy generation.» - T., 2014. - P. 37-41.
8. Masharipova G.K. The role of the resolution «Spirituality and religious tolerance» in the fight against terrorist threats in the world // Materials of the republican scientific and practical seminar on the topic «Factors of threats to spirituality in the context of globalization» - Tashkent, February 6, 2019. - Pages 23-27.
9. Masharipova G.K. Modern approaches to the process of globalization and the problem of intercultural integration // Online republican scientific and theoretical conference on the topic «Topical issues of ideological education of our people in the context of independence.» May 5, 2020. - P. 521-524.
10. Khodzhanova T.J. Dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy on

the topic «Ideological prevention - a factor in the ideological protection of the younger generation (socio-philosophical analysis)». - Samarkand, 2021. - 140 p.

11. The idea of national independence is the main concept and principles. - Tashkent: «Uzbekistan», 2000.

12. Masharipova G.K. The influence of the natural science, socio-philosophical and spiritual heritage of scientists of the Khorezm Academy of Mamun on the development of social thought. Monograph. - - Tashkent: Publishing House «Navruz», 2019. - 364 p.

13. Abu Rayhan al-Biruni. India. Volume II. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, NMIU, 2022.